

Blockchain Technology- A Panacea to Circularity in the Indian Apparel Industry

Ahmed Ashraf Zaidi^{1*} & Rahul Chandra²

¹Amity School of Fashion Technology, Amity University, Noida

²National Institute of Fashion Technology, Kangra, Himachal Pradesh

Abstract:

This study presents a review of the literature on circular economy supply chain management (CESCM) in the Indian apparel industry utilising blockchain technology (BT). With an increasing emphasis on sustainable business processes, CESCM research is gaining popularity. As a disruptive technology, BT has the ability to influence the CESCM. Using existing literature, the antecedents of CESCM employing BT have been determined, which will enable future research to develop a conceptual model of CESCM using BT for Indian apparel organisations.

Keywords: *Apparel, Blockchain technology adoption, Circularity, Circular Economy, Fashion, Textiles, supply chain management.*

*Corresponding Author:

Mr. Ahmed Ashraf Zaidi

Amity School of Fashion Technology,

Amity University,

Amity Road, Sector 125,

Noida – 201301 UP

E-mail: ahmedashrafzaidi@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Increased affordability and consumerism have led to frequent replacement, which has slowed the adoption of the circular economy and increased waste; hence more reason to identify ways and means to emphasise technologies which can help achieve the objective.

Globally, practitioners and academics are struggling to design and develop a circular economy supply chain (CESC). Implementing CESCM in the Indian apparel industry is made more difficult due to the complex nature of the supply chain, which consists of physically separated, multi-echelon entities seeking to maximise their own profits. This complexity is exacerbated by factors such as globalisation, diverse regulatory policies, irrational human behaviour, and cultural influences, among others [1]. Inefficient transactions, deception, theft, and underperforming supply chains result in a lack of trust and necessitate a system that is transparent and able to provide real-time information sharing and verification.

Currently, supply chains rely on systems such as enterprise resource planning (ERP) that store information in a centralised location most of the time. This ERP or similar systems have their own flaws. In addition, the lack of trust among supply chain members further complicates matters. This centralised system also has a single point of failure, making it vulnerable to attack, corruption, and hacking [2]. In the realm of CESCM, validation and verification are of strategic importance, as processes, products, and events within the supply chain must meet specific sustainability criteria and certifications [3]. The crucial question is therefore whether the current supply chain information systems can support the information required for the timely provenance of goods and services in a secure, transparent, and trustworthy manner. Improving supply chain transparency, safety, resilience, and process veracity is the solution to this complicated problem. The solution to this issue could be blockchain technology (BT).

BT is an emerging technology that is disrupting the market and broadening the horizons of business. BT employs a decentralised "trustless" database that enables high-volume transactions and process disintermediation, as well as decentralisation between contracting parties [4]. Blockchain possesses all the characteristics that can enable diverse supply chain participants to coordinate their actions to achieve a common objective. A significant application of BT is the identification of social and ecological conditions that may pose safety, health, or environmental concerns [5]. Nonetheless, BT faces adoption challenges in Indian apparel industry supply chain networks, particularly on the technological, behavioural, policy-oriented, and organisational fronts, just like any other disruptive technology [6]. These issues require further investigation because they affect both practice and research. This study specifically attempts to answer the following question:

What are the enablers for the Indian apparel industry to adopt CE supply chain management using blockchain technology?

2. Problem statement

Blockchain for Circular Economy (CE) seems promising; however, as per the literature review, the adoption is slow in Indian apparel retail organisations closing the loop.

3. Objective of the study

To identify the enablers for adopting blockchain technology for circular economy in the Indian apparel retail industry.

4. Literature Review

4.1 From a Linear to a Circular Economy- Why?

Global demand-supply trends draw attention to the discrepancy between the availability of finite resources and demand. Environmental degradation, volatility in prices and depletion of resources have emerged from the rising competition[7]. The burden on resources has increased tremendously because of various reasons:

1. Population growth [8]
2. Rapid development and expansion of the fashion industry, fast-changing fashion trends, global-scale mass manufacturing model, extension of production to developing countries and the landfill of waste have significantly contributed to increased environmental issues [9]
3. Pilot survey of brands and suppliers in the Indian textile sector was carried out (sample size of 570 consumers in Delhi & Bangalore) and key concerns highlighted are as follows [10] (study done by Centre for responsive business on application of circular Economy in Indian Apparel & Textile sector):
 - a. Huge fabric waste: As revealed by several suppliers, a lot of fabric waste, about one ton, is disposed of in landfills each month.
 - b. The report identifies Blockchain technology adoption for waste mapping and traceability as a long-term intervention.

4.2 Circular Economy: An organisational perspective

From an organisational perspective, a comprehensive working definition of CE by Alhawari [11] is as below:

"CE is the set of organisational planning processes for creating and delivering products, components, and materials at their highest utility for customers and society through effective and efficient utilisation of ecosystem, economic, and product cycles by closing loops for all the related resource flows."

Alhawari goes on to state, "Organizational CE activities are actions that occur in developing infrastructure and relationships with different actors to achieve material efficiency through closing ecological loops. In essence, CE is a set of practices aimed to keep products in use as long as possible even after the end of their lives." [11]

4.3 Barriers to circular economy: An organisational perspective

Several studies have addressed barriers and obstacles to CE adoption specifically for the textile industry as per research done by A. Abdelmeguid et al. [12] A. Abdelmeguid et al. carried out a systematic literature review to investigate the challenges of CE implementation in the fashion industry summarised in Table 1 [12].

Table 1- Systematisation of challenges for circular textile supply chains

Category	Challenge	Definition	Contextualization in the apparel and textile industry	Author
Economic and financial viability	1.Higher investments	Increased investments and decoupling between expenses and revenues may cause CE solutions providers to experience longer payback periods.	Fashion brands face risks in uncharted waters like circular redesign, renting models, and textile reuse, resulting in higher costs and reduced competitiveness.	S. Claxton and A. Kent [12]
	2. Financial risks	Financial risks could be incurred by CE solution providers (for example, because of servitization).		
	3. Operational risks	CE solution providers face financial and operational risks.		
Market and competition	1.Cannibalization	Circular product annihilation reduces profits and sales for businesses.	New circular textile products could cannibalize the clothing market, potentially compromising quality and damaging a company's reputation, both spatially and over time.	Y. F. Huang, S. G. Azevedo, T. J. Lin, C. S. Cheng, and C. T. Lin [13]
	2.Know-how access	Third-party CE operations may compromise device technology control.		
	3.Lower Brand Image	Third-party CE tasks can harm OEM brand reputation.		
Product characteristics	1.Fashion change	Long-lasting products struggle to adapt to fashion trends.	Fast fashion uses cheaper materials, but textiles cannot be recycled due to color separation and plastic/metal content.	A. Abdelmeguid, M. Afy-Shararah, and K. Salonitis. Yarim [12]
	2.Product complexity	Complex product design challenges recovery processes due to poisonous ingredients.		
	3.Mass customisation	Mass customization increases recovery procedures complexity.		
Standards and regulation	1.Taxation and incentives unaligned	Current tax laws and incentives do not support CE.	Legislative frameworks lack incentives for circular clothing design and textile waste reduction, hindering a comprehensive policy framework and standardization.	I. Kazancoglu, Y. Kazancoglu, E. Yarimoglu, and A. Kahraman [14]
	2.Measures, metrics, indicators unaligned	Metrics and indicators do not align with CE.		

	3.Lack of standards	Current processes, activities, materials do not meet CE standards.		
Supply chain management	1.Return flows uncertainty	Uncertainty over end-of-use product returns quantity, quality, timing, location.	Ineffective communication, integration, and cooperation among supply chain members contribute to low clothing waste, increased transportation, challenges in finding partners, lack of textile product traceability, and internal resistance to change.	E. F. Dulia, S. M. Ali, M. Garshasbi, and G. Kabir [15]
	2.Increase in transportation	CE may increase transportation costs due to product return.		
	3.Availability of suitable skills and supply chain partners	Challenge finding CE partners with shared objectives and skills.		
	4.Lack of coordination and information sharing	Lack of communication and information sharing in global supply chains due to rivalry, sensitivity, and improper planning.		
	5.Lack of traceability	Product traceability lacking, hindering collection and recovery procedures.		
	6.Cultural issues	Linear lock-in, limited awareness, and resistance to change.		
Technology	1.Eco-inefficiency of processes	Costly and inefficient recovery methods like recycling.	Advanced recycling technology is needed for mixed material compositions and textile waste classification, as shredding negatively impacts quality.	Luthra et al.; Wittstruck and Teuteberg [16], [17]
	2.Technology improvements	Rapid fashion changes hinder long-lasting products from embracing technological advancements.		
	3.Data privacy and security	Privacy and security concerns may hinder intelligent product collection.		
Users' behaviour	1.Loss of ownership value	CE offerings, especially servitization, may cause loss of ownership value.	Misconceptions about green products' higher cost and lower quality hinder consumer acceptance of circular offerings.	Luthra et al.; Wittstruck and Teuteberg [16], [17]
	2.Careless behaviour	Non-owners may engage in careless product use and conservation.		

	3. Willingness to pay	Circular products may be more expensive than standard ones, potentially affecting user willingness to pay.	
--	-----------------------	--	--

4.4 Circularity - Understanding the Indian textile waste landscape

A study done by [10] Centre of Responsible Business and Fashion for Good [18] states that India generates about 7793 kilotons, or 8.5%, of the world's textile waste each year. 59% of it is recycled and used again. The remaining 41% is either degraded (19%), burned (5%), or goes to a landfill (17%).

4.5 Blockchain Technology, origin, definition, and facilitation towards the circular economy

Nakamoto introduced blockchain technology in 2009, utilizing data mining and bitcoin techniques for data structure, ensuring high transparency and security in online storage [19].

At its core, BC is a distributed ledger that stores its users' transaction histories in blocks [20]. After each successful transaction, a new block allowing access by any network node [21]. It uses a consensus method to eliminate the need for a trusted third party, ensure data consistency, and prevent fraudulent storage in a distributed system [22].

The critical characteristics of BT include - immutability [23]; decentralization [24]; disintermediation [25]; security [26]; privacy [24]; automation [27]; smart contracts [24]; trust [28]; transparency [29]; traceability [28]; information sharing [27]. These characteristics of the BC have been recognised as a facilitator of the CE.

5. Research methodology

Systematic review of literature(SLR) on circular economy(CE) and Blockchain technology for identification of gaps

SLR on CE

- Step 1- Search using relevant combination of key words using textile+ clothing + fashion+ circular economy on google scholar and Scopus from 2011-2022
- Step 2- Resulted in 935 articles
- Step 3- Removal of duplicates resulting in 482 articles
- Step 4- Reading of title and abstract to answer questions – what is meant by circular economy; strategies that support CE; barriers to adoption of CE
- Step 5 Removal of articles that do not answer the question resulted in 135 articles

SLR on blockchain technology(BT)

- Step 1- Search using relevant combination of key word using sustainability transition + circular economy +reverse logistics+ blockchain barriers and enablers + fashion + textiles, clothing , apparel on google scholar + Scopus from 2011-2022
- Step 2- Resulted in 280 articles
- Step 3- Search included papers and review papers resulted in 200 articles
- Step 3- Reading of title and abstract to answer the questions what is BT; how can BT aid in CE and CSCM in ; what are the enables for adoption of BT for CE; resulted in 124 article

SLR on CE + BT

- Step 1- Reading of title and abstract to answer questions – what is meant by circular economy; strategies that support CE; barriers to adoption of CE & what is BT; how can BT aid in CE and CSCM in ; what are the enables for adoption of BT for CE
- Step 2 Removal of articles that do not answer the above questions resulted in 85 articles

6. Circular economy supply chain management (CESM) enablers for blockchain technology

The transition towards a circular economy faces challenges in various sectors, including the textile and apparel industry [30], which faces challenges in achieving circular transparency [31] and reverse logistics [32] for recycling initiatives. The globalized, complex supply chain requires extensive commitment, communication, and engagement among stakeholders [33].

Fashion designers face challenges in making sustainable decisions due to corporate profit targets, limited recycling materials, quality concerns, and lack of knowledge about sustainability and environmental impact. The transition to a circular economy is hindered by inadequate policies and workforce knowledge [34].

Businesses often view waste as a cost, hindering efforts to close the resource loop. Recycling materials is expensive and challenging due to the diverse mix of materials, colors, and finishers [35]. The lack of technology is a critical barrier to developing a circular economy, as it does not return the same quality product [30].

Lack of consumer interest and awareness hinders the transition towards a circular economy [30]. Returning used products requires commitment and new relationships with producers. Low collection rates in developed countries and lack of textile collection programs in developing nations make it challenging to convince customers to adopt circular business models [36].

End-of-life circularity faces challenges in collection and sorting schemes, necessitating innovative technologies to improve accuracy and speed. Retailers face challenges in reverse logistics management due to cost, staff, and procedures, requiring effective information systems for decision-making and resource management [37].

To mainstream the circular economy, several requirements must be met, including reversing cycles for material reuse, new business models, circular product design, and system conditions. Blockchain technology can provide information technology infrastructure, supporting resource efficiency, renewable input sourcing, and material recovery, particularly in recycling and refurbishing.

BT's data management can help the upstream and downstream flows of material and information reliably and transparently. This flow of material and information will have positive outcomes, such as higher customisation, reduced surveillance cost, and holistic management practices to serve the ultimate customer [38]. Finally, using BT, the sustainability initiatives will be successfully implemented throughout the entire supply chain to achieve the triple bottom-line targets for economic, environmental, and social performance.

The economic benefits are easier to observe, and published literature establishes that BT helps increase the wealth of the partnering firms [39].

BT reduces malpractice, ensures human rights adherence, and promotes sustainable performance. Clear product history records boost customer confidence, and BT addresses environmental concerns and reduces recalls.

Real-time authentication of green products boosts buyer confidence and increases willingness to pay. "Black box" reverse logistics for recycling initiatives enhances consumer trust in sustainability-focused companies.

BT offers transparency and traceability in the supply chain, but adoption is slow and limited to high-end designer labels and expensive yarns, with no standardization in the platform.

Even though the benefits of BT in CESC have been extensively enumerated, its adoption by the Indian apparel industry has been relatively slow. As BT is a disruptive technology, people are wary of its use in CESC. Members of the supply chain must comprehend and prepare for these obstacles. The author determined the following enablers for BT in SSCM based on published literature. While compiling the final enablers, the opinions of experts were also considered. Table 2 contains a listing of these factors.

Table 2 - Enablers for CESC implementation

S. No.	Enablers	Brief Description	Author
1.	Top Management support	The board of directors oversees organizational goals, vision, strategic decisions, and promoting a circular economy culture within the company.	J. Wolf [40]
2.	Infrastructure	Supply chain companies manage material and immaterial resources for sustainable activities, including reverse logistics infrastructure and used goods collection.	A. Diabat, D. Kannan, and K. Mathiyazhagan [57]
3.	Financial Constraints	Raising funds for CESC operations involves effective resource utilization and developing metrics to assess performance.	A. Chaabane, A. Ramudhin, and M. Paquet [43]
4.	Planning & Execution	Execute CESC process planning, simplify execution, and educate key parties.	A. Diabat, D. Kannan, and K. Mathiyazhagan [57]
5.	Culture	Culture encompasses beliefs, values, symbols, and presumptions shaping a company's business practices.	M. Mettler [50]
6.	Information communication and Technology (ICT)	Utilizing advanced technology for efficient traceability and product recovery after use or end of useful life.	A. Diabat, D. Kannan, and K. Mathiyazhagan [46]
7.	Customer Acceptance	Promotes CE philosophy throughout hierarchy, providing assistance to downstream clients. Awareness campaigns can change consumer attitudes towards refurbished goods. Modernized marketing tactics and increased consumer awareness drive demand for circular products.	Y. Liu and Y. Bai [51]
8.	Supplier Acceptance	The organization assists upstream suppliers and ensures sustainability attitudes are passed down to suppliers, fostering awareness and actively demanding sustainable goods and services.	P. van Loon, C. Delagarde, L. N. Van Wassenhove, and A. Mihelič [52]
9.	Government Support	Regulatory bodies shape laws and regulations affecting CESC initiatives.	S. Al Zaabi, N. Al Dhaheri, and A. Diabat [53]
10.	Competition	Group of businesses serving similar consumer groups, creating comparable goods or services, strategic component influencing CESC.	S. Saberi, M. Kouhizadeh, J. Sarkis, and L. Shen [54]
11.	External Stakeholders	Industry and institutions that do not directly benefit economically from the CESC processes are considered external stakeholders.	S. Saberi, M. Kouhizadeh, J. Sarkis, and L. Shen [54]
12.	People	Any and all staff members who significantly contribute to the CESC processes.	H. Kagermann, W.-D. Lukas, and W. Wahlster [55]

This paper provides initial thoughts and insights regarding the adoption of blockchain technology (BT) for CESC in the Indian apparel industry and how it may help SC players, policymakers, regulators, organisations, etc. use BT as a valid and efficient tool for CESC. There are several advantages of BT in CESC (e.g., access to confidential data, security protocols, improved communications among all key players, etc.), as well as opportunities and

challenges in the near future (e.g., improving performance outcomes, creation of smart devices, etc.). (e.g., readiness of SC players, lack of adequate regulations, loss of private data and identity, etc.). However, there are few obstacles to CESC adoption of BT. First, BT by itself is not suitable for large data storage, despite the fact that there are various workarounds. Secondly, there are obstacles to cryptocurrency adoption, most notably regulation. It should be made clear that cryptocurrency is not required for the creation of blockchain-based value. Thirdly, costs associated with the BT must be considered. BT requires substantial infrastructure and software investments. Who will lead the effort and how? Does the expenditure outweigh the returns? Fourth, resistance to change may be another significant obstacle. Numerous supply chain (SC) players may be threatened by BT's transparency. How will the managers implement this change? How does the end consumer perceive the CESC initiatives and how much value does he or she place on them? As BT is an emerging technology, these issues will gain clarity over time.

7. Conclusions

BT is rapidly establishing itself as a disruptive innovation in the field of technology, altering work environments and gaining widespread adoption across other sectors however its adoption is slow in the Indian apparel industry. As with any other study, this one has its limitations. First, it challenges the generalizability of the results by incorporating the opinions of a small group of experts. Second, because BT is still in its infancy and undergoing rapid transformation, this study may not have taken full advantage of emerging technology. Thirdly, because the current study focuses on India, it may not capture the challenges faced by other developing nations due to differences in factors such as culture, government support, etc. To uncover new dimensions, this study could be enhanced by adopting a mixed-method approach, such as interpretive structural modelling (ISM) with system dynamics or ISM with case study. Aspects such as carbon footprints, greenhouse gas emissions, etc., could be accurately captured with BT by tracing the complete process from the raw material supplier to the final consumer, thereby allowing for research on holistic circular economy supply chain management. With the implementation of BT in CESC, the roles and responsibilities of various supply chain partners would shift, thus challenging the currently accepted theories. This presents an opportunity to expand the circular economy's supply chain domain's body of knowledge.

References:

- [1] D. Ivanov, A. Dolgui, and B. Sokolov, "The impact of digital technology and Industry 4.0 on the ripple effect and supply chain risk analytics," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, (vol. 57, no. 3), (pp. 829–846), (Feb. 2019), doi: 10.1080/00207543.2018.1488086
- [2] F. Dong, P. Zhou, Z. Liu, D. Shen, Z. Xu, and J. Luo, "Towards a fast and secure design for enterprise-oriented cloud storage systems," in *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, (Oct. 2017), (vol. 29, no. 19), p. e4177. doi: 10.1002/cpe.4177
- [3] J. H. Grimm, J. S. Hofstetter, and J. Sarkis, "Critical factors for sub-supplier management: A sustainable food supply chains perspective," *Int. J. Prod. Econ.*, (vol. 152), (pp. 159–173), (2014), doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2013.12.011
- [4] M. C. (Google), N. (Yahoo), P. P. (Yahoo), S. V. (Samsung R. America), and V. K. (Fairchild Semiconductor), "BlockChain Technology: Beyond Bitcoin," *Appl. Innov. Rev.*, (vol. 27, no. 2), (pp. 1–16), (2016), doi: 10.15358/0935-0381-2015-4-5-222
- [5] R. Adams, B. Kewell, and G. Parry, "Blockchain for Good? Digital Ledger Technology and Sustainable Development Goals," in *World Sustainability Series*, Springer, (2018), (pp. 127–140). doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-67122-2_7
- [6] V. L. Lemieux, "Trusting records: is Blockchain technology the answer?," *Rec. Manag. J.*, (vol. 26, no. 2), (pp. 110–139), (Jul. 2016), doi: 10.1108/RMJ-12-2015-0042
- [7] F. Di Maio and P. C. Rem, "A Robust Indicator for Promoting Circular Economy through Recycling," *J. Environ. Prot. (Irvine, Calif.)*, (vol. 06, no. 10), (pp. 1095–1104), (2015), doi: 10.4236/jep.2015.610096
- [8] T. Tse, M. Esposito, and S. Khaled, "How Businesses Can Support a Circular Economy How Businesses Can Support a Circular Economy," *Harv. Bus. Rev.*, no. (February), (pp. 1–6), (2016), Accessed: Dec. 13, 2022. [Online] Available: <https://hbr.org/2016/02/how-businesses-can-support-a-circular-economy>
- [9] I. M. Sandvik and W. Stubbs, "Circular fashion supply chain through textile-to-textile recycling," *J. Fash. Mark. Manag.*, (vol. 23, no. 3), (pp. 366–381), (Aug. 2019), doi: 10.1108/JFMM-04-2018-0058
- [10] CRB, "Application of circular economy: Indian apparel & textile sector," in <https://c4rb.org/insights/report/Application-of-Circular-Economy.pdf>, (2019). doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-91971-3_8
- [11] O. Alhawari, U. Awan, M. K. S. Bhutta, and M. Ali Ülkü, "Insights from circular economy literature: A review of extant definitions and unravelling paths to future research," *Sustain.*, (vol. 13, no. 2), (pp. 1–22), (2021), doi: 10.3390/su13020859
- [12] A. Abdelmeguid, M. Afy-Shararah, and K. Salonitis, "Investigating the challenges of applying the principles of the Elsevier," (pp. 505–518), (Jul. 01, 2022). doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2022.05.009
- [13] Y. F. Huang, S. G. Azevedo, T. J. Lin, C. S. Cheng, and C. T. Lin, "Exploring the decisive barriers to achieve circular economy: Strategies for the textile innovation in Taiwan," *Sustain. Prod. Consum.*, (vol. 27), (pp. 1406–1423), (Jul. 2021), doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2021.03.007
- [14] I. Kazancoglu, Y. Kazancoglu, E. Yarimoglu, and A. Kahraman, "A conceptual framework for barriers of circular supply chains for sustainability in the textile industry," *Sustain. Dev.*, (vol. 28, no. 5), (pp. 1477–1492), (Sep. 2020), doi:

- [15] E. F. Dulia, S. M. Ali, M. Garshasbi, and G. Kabir, "Admitting risks towards circular economy practices and strategies: An empirical test from supply chain perspective," *J. Clean. Prod.*, (vol. **317**), (2021), doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128420
- [16] S. Luthra, D. Garg, and A. Haleem, "Critical success factors of green supply chain management for achieving sustainability in Indian automobile industry," *Prod. Plan. Control*, (vol. **26**, no. **5**), (pp. 339–362), (Apr. 2015), doi: 10.1080/09537287.2014.904532
- [17] D. Wittstruck and F. Teuteberg, "Integrating the concept of sustainability into the partner selection process: A fuzzy-AHP-TOPSIS approach," *Int. J. Logist. Syst. Manag.*, (vol. **12**, no. **2**), (pp. 195–226), (2012), doi: 10.1504/IJLSM.2012.047221
- [18] A. Mohan *et al.*, "Sorting for Circularity : India Wealth in Waste India ' S Potential To Bring Textile Waste Back Into," *Fash. Good*, no. (July, 2022)
- [19] S. Nakamoto, "Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System," *Decentralized Bus. Rev.*, (2008), doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3977007
- [20] J. Yli-Huumo, D. Ko, S. Choi, S. Park, and K. Smolander, "Where is current research on Blockchain technology? - A systematic review," *PLoS One*, (vol. **11**, no. **10**), (Oct. 2016), doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0163477
- [21] Z. Zheng, S. Xie, H. Dai, X. Chen, and H. Wang, "An Overview of Blockchain Technology: Architecture, Consensus, and Future Trends," in *Proceedings - 2017 IEEE 6th International Congress on Big Data, BigData Congress 2017*, (2017), (pp. 557–564). doi: 10.1109/BigDataCongress.2017.85
- [22] H. Wang, B. Ma, and R. Bai, "The spillover effect of greenwashing behaviours: an experimental approach," *Mark. Intell. Plan.*, (vol. **38**, no. **3**), (pp. 283–295), (May 2020), doi: 10.1108/MIP-01-2019-0006/FULL/PDF
- [23] M. Kouhizadeh and J. Sarkis, "Blockchain practices, potentials, and perspectives in greening supply chains," *Sustain.*, (vol. **10**, no. **10**), (2018), doi: 10.3390/su10103652
- [24] P. Centobelli, R. Cerchione, D. Chiaroni, P. Del Vecchio, and A. Urbinati, "Designing business models in circular economy: A systematic literature review and research agenda," *Bus. Strateg. Environ.*, (vol. **29**, no. **4**), (pp. 1734–1749), (May 2020), doi: 10.1002/bse.2466
- [25] M. Kouhizadeh, Q. Zhu, and J. Sarkis, "Blockchain and the circular economy: potential tensions and critical reflections from practice," *Prod. Plan. Control*, (vol. **31**, no. **11–12**), (pp. 950–966), (2020), doi: 10.1080/09537287.2019.1695925
- [26] R. Cole, M. Stevenson, and J. Aitken, "Blockchain technology: implications for operations and supply chain management," *Supply Chain Manag.*, (vol. **24**, no. **4**), (pp. 469–483), (Jun. 2019), doi: 10.1108/SCM-09-2018-0309
- [27] S. Nandi, J. Sarkis, A. A. Hervani, and M. M. Helms, "Redesigning Supply Chains using Blockchain-Enabled Circular Economy and COVID-19 Experiences," *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, (vol. **27**). (pp. 10–22), (2021). doi: 10.1016/j.spc.2020.10.019
- [28] A. Upadhyay, S. Mukhuty, V. Kumar, and Y. Kazancoglu, "Blockchain technology and the circular economy: Implications for sustainability and social responsibility," *J. Clean. Prod.*, (vol. **293**), (2021), doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126130
- [29] A. Bekrar, A. A. El Cadi, R. Todosijevic, and J. Sarkis, "Digitalizing the closing-of-the-loop for supply chains: A transportation and blockchain perspective," *Sustain.*, (vol. **13**, no. **5**), (pp. 1–25), (Mar. 2021), doi: 10.3390/su13052895
- [30] J. Kirchherr *et al.*, "Barriers to the Circular Economy: Evidence From the European Union (EU)," *Ecol. Econ.*, (vol. **150**), (pp. 264–272), (Aug. 2018), doi: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.04.028
- [31] C. W. Ki, S. M. Chong, and J. E. Ha-Brookshire, "How fashion can achieve sustainable development through a circular economy and stakeholder engagement: A systematic literature review," *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, (vol. **27**, no. **6**). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, (pp. 2401–2424), (Nov. 01, 2020). doi: 10.1002/csr.1970
- [32] S. Claxton and A. Kent, "The management of sustainable fashion design strategies: An analysis of the designer's role," *J. Clean. Prod.*, (vol. **268**), (Sep. 2020), doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122112
- [33] S. Mishra, S. Jain, and G. Malhotra, "The anatomy of circular economy transition in the fashion industry," *Soc. Responsib. J.*, (vol. **17**, no. **4**), (pp. 524–542), (2020), doi: 10.1108/SRJ-06-2019-0216
- [34] F. Jia, S. Yin, L. Chen, and X. Chen, "The circular economy in the textile and apparel industry: A systematic literature review," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, (vol. **259**). Elsevier Ltd, (Jun. 20, 2020). doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120728
- [35] K. Kant Hvass and E. R. G. Pedersen, "Toward circular economy of fashion: Experiences from a brand's product take-back initiative," *J. Fash. Mark. Manag.*, (vol. **23**, no. **3**), (pp. 345–365), (Aug. 2019), doi: 10.1108/JFMM-04-2018-0059
- [36] Ellen MacArthur Foundation, "Towards the Circular Economy," 2013. Accessed: (Dec. 08, 2022). [Online] Available: https://www.werktrends.nl/app/uploads/2015/06/Rapport_McKinsey-Towards_A_Circular_Economy.pdf
- [37] B. Su, A. Heshmati, Y. Geng, and X. Yu, "A review of the circular economy in China: Moving from rhetoric to implementation," *J. Clean. Prod.*, (vol. **42**), (pp. 215–227), (2013), doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.11.020
- [38] F. Tian, "An agri-food supply chain traceability system for China based on RFID & blockchain technology," in *2016 13th International Conference on Service Systems and Service Management, ICSSSM 2016*, (2016). doi: 10.1109/ICSSSM.2016.7538424
- [39] S. Underwood, "Blockchain beyond bitcoin," *Commun. ACM*, (vol. **59**, no. **11**), (pp. 15–17), (Oct. 2016), doi: 10.1145/2994581
- [40] J. Wolf, "Sustainable Supply Chain Management Integration: A Qualitative Analysis of the German Manufacturing Industry," *J. Bus. Ethics* 2011 1022, (vol. **102**, no. **2**), (pp. 221–235), (Feb. 2011), doi: 10.1007/S10551-011-0806-0
- [41] S. Agrawal, R. K. Singh, and Q. Murtaza, "A literature review and perspectives in reverse logistics," *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, (vol. **97**). Elsevier, (pp. 76–92), (2015). doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.02.009
- [42] J. A. Garza-Reyes, A. Salomé Valls, S. Peter Nadeem, A. Anosike, and V. Kumar, "A circularity measurement toolkit for manufacturing SMEs," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, (vol. **57**, no. **23**), (pp. 7319–7343), (Dec. 2019), doi: 10.1080/00207543.2018.1559961
- [43] A. Chaabane, A. Ramudhin, and M. Paquet, "Design of sustainable supply chains under the emission trading scheme," *Int. J. Prod. Econ.*, (vol. **135**, no. **1**), (pp. 37–49), (Jan. 2012), doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.10.025
- [44] M. A. Ferreira, C. J. C. Jabbour, and A. B. L. de Sousa Jabbour, "Maturity levels of material cycles and waste management in a context of green supply chain management: an innovative framework and its application to Brazilian

- cases,” *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manag.*, (vol. 19, no. 1), (pp. 516–525), (Jan. 2017), doi: 10.1007/s10163-015-0416-5
- [45] S. Saberi, M. Kouhizadeh, J. Sarkis, and L. Shen, “Blockchain technology and its relationships to sustainable supply chain management,” *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, (vol. 57, no. 7), (pp. 2117–2135), Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1080/00207543.2018.1533261
- [46] A. Diabat, D. Kannan, and K. Mathiyazhagan, “Analysis of enablers for implementation of sustainable supply chain management - A textile case,” *J. Clean. Prod.*, (vol. 83), (pp. 391–403), (Nov. 2014), doi: 10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2014.06.081
- [47] A. B. L. de Sousa Jabbour, F. C. D. O. Frascareli, and C. J. C. Jabbour, “Green supply chain management and firms’ performance: Understanding potential relationships and the role of green sourcing and some other green practices,” *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, (vol. 104), (pp. 366–374), (Nov. 2015), doi: 10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2015.07.017
- [48] S. Gupta, S. Kumar, S. K. Singh, C. Foropon, and C. Chandra, “Role of cloud ERP on the performance of an organization: Contingent resource-based view perspective,” *Int. J. Logist. Manag.*, (vol. 29, no. 2), (pp. 659–675), (2018), doi: 10.1108/IJLM-07-2017-0192
- [49] P. Ghadimi, C. Wang, and M. K. Lim, “Sustainable supply chain modeling and analysis: Past debate, present problems and future challenges,” *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, (vol. 140), (pp. 72–84), (2019), doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.09.005
- [50] M. Mettler, “Blockchain technology in healthcare: The revolution starts here,” in *2016 IEEE 18th International Conference on e-Health Networking, Applications and Services, Healthcom 2016*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., (Nov. 2016). doi: 10.1109/HealthCom.2016.7749510
- [51] Y. Liu and Y. Bai, “An exploration of firms’ awareness and behavior of developing circular economy: An empirical research in China,” *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, (vol. 87), (pp. 145–152), (2014), doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2014.04.002
- [52] P. van Loon, C. Delagarde, L. N. Van Wassenhove, and A. Mihelič, “Leasing or buying white goods: comparing manufacturer profitability versus cost to consumer,” *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, (vol. 58, no. 4), (pp. 1092–1106), (Feb. 2020), doi: 10.1080/00207543.2019.1612962
- [53] S. Al Zaabi, N. Al Dhaheri, and A. Diabat, “Analysis of interaction between the barriers for the implementation of sustainable supply chain management,” *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.*, (vol. 68, no. 1–4), (pp. 895–905), (Apr. 2013), doi: 10.1007/s00170-013-4951-8
- [54] M. Kouhizadeh, S. Saberi, and J. Sarkis, “Blockchain technology and the sustainable supply chain: Theoretically exploring adoption barriers,” *Int. J. Prod. Econ.*, (vol. 231), (p. 107831), (Jan. 2021), doi: 10.1016/J.IJPE.2020.107831
- [55] H. Kagermann, W.-D. Lukas, and W. Wahlster, “Industry 4.0: On the way to the 4th industrial revolution with the Internet of Things - ingénieur.de,” *INGENIEUR.de*, (2011). https://www-live.dfki.de/fileadmin/user_upload/DFKI/Medien/News_Media/Presse/Presse-Highlights/vdinach2011a13-ind4.0-Internet-Dinge.pdf (accessed Sep. 01, 2022)